

NURSE'S EFFORTS TO TRANSFORM OF NURSE ROLES IN PRIMARY HEALTH CARE FROM PROMOTIVE TO CURATIVE IN MANAGING PATIENTS WITH ACS IN PRIMARY HEALTH CARE MALANG REGENCY, EAST JAVA, INDONESIA

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ABSTRACT

Background: Acute Coronary Syndrome (ACS) is a sudden reduction disorder in the coronary bloodstream that is life-threatening and as a source of morbidity and mortality. Nurses in Primary Health Care have an important role for health problems in the community in a preventive, curative, and rehabilitation. This requires that the role nurses not only do promotive actions but also curative in handling patients with ACS.

Purpose: The purpose of this study was to explore nurses in primary health care had an important role to transform from promotive but also curative managing Patients with ACS in Primary Health Care.

Methods: This research used qualitative method with descriptive-phenomenological approach by using the process of analysis of Clark and Brown, 2013.

Results: Four themes were successfully obtained from 8 participants, namely: Efforts to improve quality, Harmony team in Collaboration, The Need for improving nurse quality, Multi-working of nurse with additional duty.

Discussion: The implementation of emergency care services at the primary health care was based on the nurses' awareness of roles in providing holistic nursing care to patients with ACS related to prompt and appropriate relief in order to save the lives of patients. The role of nurses from the focus to the community was promotive but now requires nurses to have good skills in curative actions. Therefore, it is necessary to develop nurses' skills to continue to improve the service of patients with ACS in the primary health care so that they can become the first level of health services that are relied on by the community.

Key words: Nurses role, Acute Coronary Syndrome, Emergency Nursing, Primary Health Care.

INTRODUCTION

Acute Coronary Syndrome (ACS) is a life-threatening condition (Amsterdam, 2014). This is a sudden reduction disorder in the coronary bloodstream that is life-threatening and as a source of morbidity and mortality (Kim, 2008)]. Management of patients with ACS depends on the speed of time and immediate action. Salvage in

cardiac arrest decreases from 7-10% every minute in the delay of therapy (Aringhieri, Bruni, Khodaparasti, & van Essen, 2017). Puskesmas nurses have an important role to play in addressing common health problems in the community in a preventive, curative, and rehabilitation manner (Carrier, Halcomb, & Davidson, 2015). The role of nurses in the past few decades

was dubbed as prolonged arm, extended role doctrine, *verlengde arm theorie* As Bene and Bennis have said deeply foster 1986. This illustrates that nurses as "prolonged arm, of the doctor's hand" means the impression of the dependence of the nurse's role on the doctor. This assumption began to fade in 1985 the nurse's stigma of "prolonged arm, of the doctor's hand" turned into a partnership. The role of primary health care according Satrianegara (2014), primary health care has a function as a center for driving health-oriented development, a center for community empowerment, a first-level health service center covering individual health services (private goods) and public health services (public goods). The role of primary health care organizes first-level public health efforts (UKM) and individual health efforts (UKP). The primary health care services prioritize promotive, preventive, curative and rehabilitative efforts to achieve the highest degree of public health in the working area (Ministry Of Health RI, 2014). That the reason why primary health care must be first level public health care have emergency service. Emergency services at the health center as a first-level health facility services. This requires nurses to provide immediate medical help and treatment. The purpose of this study is to explore role of nurses' experiences in transforming promotive to curative roles. In Treating Patients With ACS In Primary Health Care especially emergency room at Turen, Malang, East Java Indonesia.

METHODS

Study Design

This research is conducted by using a descriptive-qualitative method. A descriptive phenomenological design was used in this research to understand in-depth the nurses' experiences. This research was

conducted within 4 months, starting from September to December 2017.

Setting

This research was conducted in Primary Health Care of Turen, Malang Regency, East Java, Indonesia.

Research Subject

Participants of this study were 8 nurses working who have aged 3 years until 15 years experience at primary health service. From education level, there were seven participants who had Diploma III of nursing and there was one participant who was a nursing bachelor. The training attended by the nurses were BCLAS, BTLS.

Instruments

The interviews were conducted with in-depth interviews, semi-structured interview techniques, and interview guides. The process of data analysis was done directly with transcripts and theme determination. After the theme has been collected, the analysis is performed by using thematic analysis method. The researchers also read the materials repeatedly to find meaning and pattern. After that, several initial codes were made with color on keywords continued with theme defining, repeating theme to set as the main theme, define theme again, and produce and write the finished theme of analysis. The results will be presented in the form of keywords, categories, sub-themes, and research themes.

Data Analysis

Interview data were obtained by making verbatim transcripts. Then the researchers performed data analysis by using thematic analysis of Clark and Brown (2013). The process of thematic analysis was as follows six steps. Data analysis was done manually, this was because the

research results contained nurse expression about experience that could not be analyzed with software.

Ethical Consideration

The researcher conducted ethical clearance process and was approved by the ethics committee of Faculty of Medicine of Brawijaya University with number 216/EC/KEPK/06/2017.

RESULTS

The research results that were obtained based on the purpose of research obtained three themes, namely:

Table 1. Themes, Sub-themes, and Statements Supporting Participants' Nurse's role Experience in Primary Health Care of Turen, Malang Regency, East Java, Indonesia (n = 8).

No	Theme	Sub theme	Keywords
1	Efforts to improve quality,	Critical thinking demands in nursing	<i>" sometimes nurses careful from patient complaints in examination leads anywhere so it we are also one of action right later on, complaint of heartburn turns out after check by ECG there is a problem but some people say that there is chest pain even though there's nothing, so, it must be more careful in checking for physical examination and history (P1) "</i> <i>The change is the mindset for handling, ranging orderly communication to holders also discipline program. had no purpose. If the first alone is not so solid. Now, they know the pattern of communication. (P6)</i>
		Creativity and responsiveness demand in nursing	<i>...we bought our own saturation tester and thermometers because we need it much. We did not want to wait any longer since patients came every day. (P7)</i> <i>This has been the nursing competency that we should keep running and documenting with full of responsibility. (P1, P2)</i>
2	Harmony team in Collaboration	Sharing knowledge and experience in service	<i>There is hardly any training, so we studied the related cases with the current doctor, and there is no formal training. (P3, P2)</i>
3	The Need for improving nurse quality	Infrastructure & facilities needs	<i>... building a network is also the duty of all people and parties how to build a good system that is fast transporting, communicating, how to get patients at these ends in the peripheral areas to be handled properly. So far patients in this peripheral in basic services has been faster but it goes beyond help for long. If the dream does exist outside the country such as the transport helicopter fast cannot waste time (P6)</i> <i>Patients were considered in bed P1 prepared with emergency box making it easier specialized patient observation (P5)</i> <i>I think less like defib we have the tools but has not been used. And may take the training again. Sometimes the tools are not appropriate for example orders continue pad right English is also disposable, so it is less effective because of things like that. If more exist and need to be completed again. (P6)</i> <i>limited ability and have been imagined unable, do not want to study this normal ECG like this, if a heart attack should be like this (P8)</i>
		Personal development needs	<i>What the nurse does when he/she found the data was to automatically do a consultation with doctors. The policy is in the hand of the doctor, we cannot include the results of ECG. I only take the photo and gave it to the doctor (P4).</i> <i>Not all nurses participate in training, the nurses can read about it themselves, but they are afraid that it will be wrong, because the medicine also depends on the results of electrocardiography. Thus, I gave the photo of the results of electrocardiography when I call the doctor (P5)</i>
4	Multi-working of nurse with additional duty	Patients want to be served as soon as possible	<i>Patients want to be served quickly while the nurse yes giving action, the drug serve patients. (P5)</i>
		Double job	<i>Multi working nurse role a lot. Sometimes in community not only at emergency room(P6)</i> <i>We are double job, so our weaknesses in the person service are not as detailed as possible in the minds of people with thoughts. Because in service so much, in primary health care not specifically. sometimes in the emergency room and in community with multivariate diseases. including coronary syndrome, we handle it. (P6)</i>

DISCUSSION

Transformed health services from hospital-centered to primary health care providers in the community in the region. The goal is to help the community to access health services easily and so that people get quality health care and equal for all levels regardless of socioeconomic status, and all these things are expected to be realized through the efforts of primary health care. This affects the role of nurses from the community to focus on the promotion but now requires nurses have a good skill in curative action. The need for a care workforce is now drawing attention in many countries on health services (Grant, Lines, Darbyshire, & Parry, 2017).

The ideal role of nurses is to provide services based on nursing knowledge and tips. A nurse carries a very important function and role in providing holistic nursing care to clients but participants cannot provide holistic nursing care in the emergency room. The actual duties of nurses are listed in Law No. 38 of 2014 concerning Nursing article 29 paragraph 1 letter a state that nurses are assigned as providers of Nursing Care. This is not in accordance with the conditions in the field that there is no documentation of nursing care at the Puskesmas IGD. Besides the discrepancy answer participants in determining nursing diagnoses. This happens because the nurses are not used to doing it. Something that was never done will make someone forget something. Based on the formulation of nursing diagnoses, nurses will more clearly determine the action (Nursalam, 2011).

Efforts to Improve Quality

Quality improvement efforts are measured by a system consisting of three components: input, process and output. First, the component input in the planning of human resources with the recruitment

process organized by the government to ensure the quality of human resources. Nurses were able to change the mindset, in addition to the training needs required by the nurse will also improve the quality. So that the output is expected with improvement efforts can provide an excellent service to patients in primary health care Malang. According to Kim (2008) nurses perform on a voluntary basis in equipping equipment and medicines. Nurses take a proactive approach to solve the problem and identify. The ideal role of nurses is to provide services based on nursing knowledge and tips. A nurse carries a very important function and role in providing holistic nursing care to clients but participants cannot provide holistic nursing care in the emergency room. The nursing process describes a very complex and dynamic process. Nurses continually learn new skills, adjust current practices to meet their needs and develop new approaches to problem solving. Therefore, the practice of nurses is not static but is continually improved based on the level of core skills. However, within these limits it is possible to describe the field of knowledge and core competencies used by nurses. For example, from the review and process of anamneses to be complete, so it takes foresight and takes more time to do anamneses and immediately So, nurse must be need of Critical thinking demands in nursing and Creativity and responsiveness demands in nursing. According (Mehmet & Tarhan, 2016) that the assessment process is the foundation step for the process improvement activities. investigate strong, weak, and/ or missing points in definition and application. the assessment process as the quality of nursing services provided.

Harmony Team in Collaboration

Skill enhancement is needed by nurses. The involvement of doctors as the main

controller makes nurses as assistants causing gaps in collaborative practice. So that nurses feel the gap between doctors and nurses such as employers and servants (Keleher & Parker, 2013). In developed countries, New Zealand emphasizes that multidisciplinary and integration teams are patient-centered. Patients get better service when treated with a multidisciplinary team. In multidisciplinary team collaboration has their respective duties and authority where each member has the authority to make autonomous decisions (Kim & Chung, 2008). Collaboration is one of the main supporters that can improve the quality of care and healing of patients. The practice of collaboration between nurses and doctors requires knowledge, professional attitude starting from the way of communication, how to collaborate with patients and the skills of nurses in making decisions. Nurses and doctors can share knowledge and experience in service.

The Need for Improving Nurse Quality

WHO described emergency services as "a global discipline that provides secondary disease prevention and is also a tool for primary prevention? It is an integrated emergency care system consisting of access to emergency care; provision of emergency care in the community and during patient transportation; and provision of care in hospital receiving facilities or emergency departments (Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland, 2012) . The needs to improve quality such as Personal development needs & Infrastructure, facilities need. Personal development needs such as improving the quality of helpers must be balanced with the skills of nurses and the completeness of infrastructure. The need for increased skills, namely nurses need for self-development, especially the skill in saving basic life rocks / Basic life support in handling emergency cases. Because of

limitations in ability so that nurses often feel inadequate for example reading ECGs. Infrastructure, facility's needs, transportation constraints cause delays in care and treatment. The results of the research show that transportation barriers that affect access to health care in 67% of the population state that rural patients face greater transportation barriers to access health care than access in urban areas. Transportation problems are related to distance and travel time (Sharp, 2014; Mattson, 2010). The use of eHealth tools as a solution for system integration and services requires a skilled clinical informatics workforce; technical standards and software; adequate privacy and security; and clinical leadership to implement and monitor them for successful adoption. In addition, improving the quality, safety and efficiency of referrals, care and patient coordination (WHO, 2016)

Multi-working of nurses with additional duty

In this condition nurse do multi-working and patients want to be served as soon as possible beside nurse doing Double job. The role of nurse practitioners is developed in response to the shortage of nurses and increased workload. This is due to the lack of medical personnel so that the community can obtain health services. The role of the nurse is different from the role of the doctor who focuses on the diagnosis and treatment of the disease. But nurses see patients holistically which emphasizes the therapeutic relationship (Grant et al., 2017). Efforts to meet the needs of Human Resources (HR) Health have not been adequate, both the number, type, and quality of health workers needed. In addition, the distribution of health workers is still uneven.

CONCLUSION

Four themes were successfully obtained from 8 participants, namely: Efforts to improve quality, Harmony team in Collaboration, The Need for improving nurse quality, Multi-working of nurse with additional duty. The implementation of emergency care services currently running at the emergency room at the primary health care was based on the nurses' awareness of carrying out the very important functions and roles in providing holistic nursing care to clients in the handling of patients with ACS related to prompt and appropriate relief in order to save the lives of patients. The role of nurses from the focus to the community was promotive but now requires nurses to have good skills in curative actions. Therefore, it is necessary to develop nurses' skills to continue to improve the service of patients with ACS in the primary health care so that they can become the first level of health services that are relied on by the community.

SUGGESTION

The hospital is expected to prepare the patient preoperative Sectio Caesarea maximum effort to prevent the patient does not experience anxiety. Further research regarding maternity nursing management in the treatment of anxiety in patients with preoperative of Sectio Caesarea. It is expected that the public can learn more about how to reduce preoperative anxiety in patients of Sectio Caesarea. That pregnant women who will undergo the process of birth by surgery Sectio Caesarea can prepare optimally for smooth operation.

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